

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF QUALITATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Nuradinov F.R.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8403068>

***Abstract.** This article describes the system, the pedagogical system, the pedagogical conditions, their philosophical interpretation and their connection. The content of the article presents the views of academic researchers on the advisability of introducing pedagogical conditions necessary for the emergence or change of a certain pedagogical structure, including conditions that make it possible to increase the significance of its effectiveness.*

***Keywords:** System, pedagogical conditions, design, conditions, object, pedagogical activity, complex, element, competence, quality.*

To raise the quality of education in higher education institutions in our republic, to improve the educational system based on the organization of pedagogues' certification, to create new generations of primary education regulatory documents, to develop educational resources of pedagogical quality enough foundations have been created.

As we know, the optional system is available in certain conditions. Pedagogical systems are artificially calculated, therefore, in their implementation, it is necessary to pay special attention to the organization and correction of these conditions. In the philosophical use of the word "system", we understand the system, its properties depend on it, the influencers, the complex of its elements and their interrelationships.

Considering the peculiarity of the interpretation of the concept of "conditions" in pedagogy, the openness of pedagogical systems to external changes, and the fact that they are influenced by random factors, this significantly expands the field of conditions affecting them. There is a danger of including objects that have an imperceptible influence on the conditions in the study of everything that affects the pedagogical event. Philosophical interpretation of the concept of "conditions" does not allow taking into account existing or created conditions within the pedagogical system. Therefore, taking into account the opinions of N.M.Yakovleva [1] and others, we believe that philosophical interpretation unreasonably expands the set of objects necessary for the emergence, existence and change of pedagogical phenomena.

In order to solve this problem, the content, forms, methods and material-spatial aspects of education created by V.I.Andreev[2], M.Ye.Duranov[3] and others in a conscious approach to pedagogical conditions in the pedagogical process and aimed at solving specific tasks. The objective possibilities of the environment are offered by a set of criteria.

Many researchers show that it is appropriate to include the pedagogical conditions necessary for the emergence or change of a certain pedagogical construction, including those that allow for a significant increase in its effectiveness.

So, following N.M.Yakovleva[1] and others, under pedagogical conditions we understand the set of measures aimed at increasing the effectiveness of pedagogical activity.

Before starting to determine the conditions for the development of qualitative competence, we will dwell on the main factors that allow this selection to be carried out. According to the analysis

of the research works conducted by us in recent years [4], [5], researchers take into account the following aspects when determining pedagogical conditions:

- 1) modern requirements for the organization of educational processes;
- 2) the characteristic of the formed quality (competence, knowledge, skills, etc.) and researched structural features (systems, models);
- 3) the existing level of organizational-pedagogical means;
- 4) necessity and sufficiency of the complex of conditions.

We consider these bases for choosing pedagogical conditions according to the subject of our research.

First of all, the effective functioning of the system of qualitative competence development of students of higher educational institutions and the pedagogical conditions for its development are contrary to the complex legislation, the modern requirements of the state, society and the personal qualities of the specialist, the modern paradigm of education. It is necessary not to be. Secondly, the quality of development - the characteristic of qualitative competence is that it is organized from four competencies (mathematics, information, management, assessment) that are developed in sufficiently independent modules of the training system.

The peculiarity of the development system is that pedagogical quality is a relatively new scientific field, which is why scientific, methodical, educational publications are not widely distributed at the moment. Also, the use of qualitative methods requires a lot of work due to the volume of mathematical calculations. These factors reduce the cognitive activities of students and, accordingly, the effectiveness of the entire training system.

In the circumstances, the skills, qualifications and experiences of students in collecting, processing, storing and transmitting information based on modern interactive technologies are of particular importance, and it is necessary to take this into account when choosing conditions that ensure the effectiveness of qualitative training.

The breadth of the field of application of qualitative methods in pedagogic activity creates the diversity, unexpectedness and special features of the situations in which they can be used. For this reason, it is necessary to ensure the development of universal qualitative competence of students.

In such conditions, it is necessary to ensure the training of future teachers so that students of higher education institutions can identify problematic situations and express the problem in front of a mathematical expert or programmer. Repetition of similar problems should encourage the specialist to receive independent education in the field of quality.

Third, the effectiveness of the selected conditions is determined by the ratio of the achieved (intended) effectiveness and the used pedagogical tools (either existing or specially organized).

Therefore, in the development of qualitative competence, it is necessary to use the objective possibilities of the educational content, forms, methods and material-spatial environment that do not lead to excessive labor, time, and material costs. Therefore, it is necessary to use modern educational technologies to achieve maximum results from available tools.

Fourthly, as we mentioned earlier, it is not appropriate to consider all the conditions affecting the operation of the system. Therefore, we select only the important conditions that are considered necessary and sufficient to ensure the effective operation and development of the system in a comprehensive manner.

Under the necessary and sufficient conditions, we understand the complete set of conditions that “do not remove any component from the content without violating the relationship of this case”

[7], that is, do not reduce the effectiveness of the qualitative competence development system.

Thus, on the basis of modern requirements for the organization of educational processes, taking into account the characteristics of the development of qualitative competence of students and modern organizational and pedagogical tools, we have allocated the following set of conditions:

1) use of the rating system as a factor of involvement in the process of developing students' qualitative competence;

2) to give a creative character to the preparation process by using educational projects;

3) strengthening the practical orientation of qualitative training based on the use of the opportunities of the external information-educational environment.

REFERENCES

1. Яковлев Е. В., Яковлева Н. О. Педагогическая концепция: методологические аспекты построения. - М.: Гуманитар, изд. центр ВЛАДБС, 2006. - 239 с.

2. Андреев В.И. Педагогика творческого саморазвития. – Казань: Изд-во КГУ, 1996. – 568 с.

3. Дуранов М.Е. Профессионально-педагогическая деятельность и исследовательский подход к ней. Монография. - Челябинск: ЧГАКИ, 2002. - 276с.

4. Колясникова Л. В. Организационные условия подготовки педагогов профессиональной школы к диагностике результатов обучения: дис. ...канд. пед. наук. - М., 2003. - 227 с.

5. Савушкин П. Н. Организационно-педагогические условия формирования профессионально важных качеств у студентов профессионально-педагогического колледжа: дис. ... канд. пед. наук. - Брянск, 1999. - 227 с.

6. Чурсина Формирование коммуникативно-познавательных умений у студентов средствами новых информационных технологий: дис. ..канд.. пед. наук. - Челябинск, 2002. - 207 с.